

Knowledge of Postnatal Mothers regarding Respectful Maternity Care admitted in a selected Hospital, Odisha

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Abstract

Childbirth is a critical event in the life of a woman. However, pregnant women are still exposed to various forms of disrespect and abuse worldwide. World Health Organization (WHO, 2018) recommended respectful maternity care (RMC), which refers to providing supportive care without discrimination to all pregnant women. This study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding RMC. A descriptive study was conducted among 136 postnatal mothers at the selected public hospital of Odisha. Knowledge regarding RMC was assessed with the help of structured interview schedule by the researcher. 136 postnatal mothers were considered for this study and they were selected by purposive sampling technique. Data was collected with the help of Structured Interview Schedule to assess the level of knowledge regarding RMC. With regards to knowledge of mothers regarding RMC it reveals that highest 69.5% of postnatal mothers had moderate knowledge regarding respectful maternity care followed by 21% of mothers had adequate score and same numbers 9% of postnatal mothers had inadequate knowledge score & nobody had scored low level or very good knowledge regarding respectful maternity care. This showed there is an need of postnatal mothers to learn on RMC, as no one had scored the very good level..

Introduction

Every woman is anxious to have a normal baby after a long duration of pregnancy to accomplish her motherhood phase in a well-equipped hospital setting with skilled professional experts. This is not only her desire but also the fundamental rights to access, deserve quality of care. As motherhood is considered as highest crown of honour for a woman.[1,2]

Maternal mortality resulting from pregnancy and delivery complications is a sensitive indicator of women's status in the society, access to care services, and sufficiency and quality of healthcare and is the major indicator of a country's developmental status. The present study aimed at determination of guideline regarding respectful maternity care from postnatal mothers perspective.[3-5]

Every labor is unique, evidence recommends that there should not be a routine indication for medical intervention to accelerate labour or expedite birth. but today's increasing medicalization of normal childbirth processes are undermining a woman's own capability to

give birth and negatively impacting her birth experience,''. In developing countries , the need for care and support during and after birth is, until less well recognized. Despite its importance, this period is generally most neglected. [6-8]

Respectful maternity care is a universal human right due to every childbearing woman in every health system around the world. Women's experiences with maternity caregivers can empower and comfort, or inflict lasting damage and emotional trauma. [9-11]

Most of the time, interventions are aim to improve access to skilled birth care, the quality of relationships with caregivers has received less attention. Evidenced suggest that the care providing in maternity centre should enhanced in accordance to women's rights, social justice , social norm and importance to women's decision making , which a women produce a high level of satisfaction in her childbearing process. [12]

As the present health Care delivery system emphasizes more on promotion of RMC. A woman's description and perception of non-dignified care may be very context specific. RMC is also being used as a tool to educate health workers about maternity care and human rights, and to raise awareness of the problem in a way that avoids blaming and shaming. Once the Charter gained momentum, it was endorsed by the *World Health Organization, the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics, and the International Confederation of Midwives*. [13]

So the researcher decided “ To assess the knowledge level of postnatal mother on respectful maternity care ” ; so that they can aware about their fundamental rights.

Objectives:

- To assess the level of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding RMC .
- To associate the level of knowledge regarding RMC with the selected demographic and obstetrical variables of postnatal mothers

Methodology- A descriptive study was conducted among 136 postnatal mothers at the selected public hospital of Odisha. Knowledge regarding RMC was assessed with the help of structured interview schedule by the researcher. Total 136 postnatal mothers were considered for this study and they were selected by purposive sampling technique. All the mothers those present during the time of data collection and had normal vaginal delivery without any complication were considered for the study. Oral and written consent was obtained from the mother before data collection. Researcher developed the tool after reviewing the literature . Tool was consists of two parts. Part one regarding socio demographic variables and part two was knowledge regarding RMC. Knowledge questionnaire of postnatal mother on respectful maternity care consist of structured Interview schedule to assess the level of knowledge.

There are total 32 items related to RMC . Five items on right to have information , informed consent and refusal or accept for choices and preferences equality, freedom from discrimination and equitable care ,freedom from harm and ill treatment, communication, liberty, autonomy, self-determination and freedom from coercion, for dignity and respect ,confidentiality , privacy care, eighteen items for assessment regarding regarding right for timely health care, highest attainable level of health -5items and knowledge regarding Prevention of disrespect and abuse 4items. Each item has one correct answer and total score was 32.

Score Interpretation

Level of knowledge	Actual score	Percentage (%)
Very poor	0-6	< 20
Poor	7-12	21– 40
Average	13 – 19	41-60
Good	20-25	61-80
Very good	26 – 32	81-100

Data was collected after 24 hours of delivery as it was considered that the mother will feel comfortable to respond. It took around 15 to 20 mins for each mother. The collected datas planed to analyse with descriptive statistics.

Result:

majority44% (60)of postnatal mothers were in the age group of 21-25Yrs,22%(30) of postnatal mothers were in the age group of 26- 30years followed by, 19% (26) of postnatal mothers were in the age group of > 20years , 14.5%(20) were of in the age group of 31 - 45Yrs and no one (0) was within 45Yrs or more . maximum 37 %(50) of postnatal mothers were completed up to secondary education ,24% (33) were completed primary education among them12.5%(17) of postnatal mothers had no formal education and 17.5%(24) were undergone higher secondary standard & only 9 % (12)of postnatal mothers were minimally completed Graduation and above courses.maximum 67.5%(92) of postnatal mother were housewife, 22%(30) mothers were belonged to the daily wedges category and lowest 6.5%(9) of them were doing service in private as well as Govt. Sector & only 4%(5) of postnatal mother had their own business.most 58 %(79) of the postnatal mothers were from a nuclear family and 42 % (57) were from joint family.majority 48% (65)were Primi& 52% (71) were multiparus women.51% (69) had delivered male child, 49 %(67) were female child . majority 49%(67) of were delivered Live full-term baby , 30%(41) had preterm baby, 12% (16) of postnatal mothers had stillbirth baby & also 9%(12) of postnatal mothers had intrauterine fetal death in the current outcome.

With regards to knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding RMC it was showed that highest 69.5% of postnatal mothers had moderate knowledge regarding respectful maternity care followed by 21% of mothers had adequate score and 9% of postnatal mothers had inadequate knowledge score & nobody had scored low level or very good knowledge regarding respectful maternity care. This showed there is an need of postnatal mothers to learn on RMC.

Area wise maximum score, mean, standard deviation of knowledge of postnatal mother regarding respectful maternity care showed the mean and SD of knowledge scores of the postnatal mothers showed that the highest mean score (6.14+- 1.55) indicates a moderate level of knowledge among postnatal mother regarding respectful maternity care , in the area of rights of postnatal mother to have informed consent, privacy , right information , right of equality, freedom from discrimination, communication. Right to dignity and respect, Confidentiality was the maximum and Right for timely care to the highest attainable level of health was (6.01+-1.56) &for the area of concept of respectful maternity care was (2.96+- 82) and it was evident that postnatal mothers had inadequate knowledge in the field of Prevention of disrespect and abuse (4+-0.71) in the health care field.

Further item wise correct responses indicates that the majority 75% of postnatal mothers had highest score was obtained by the item “ When a mother’s Self respect is preserved by” maximum 63% correctly responds to the item “What do you mean by respectful maternity care ? ”, 61% of postnatal mothers score to the item “Which one is the wrong statement about respectful maternity care services? ”& 56% were correctly responded in the item “Which one is not a component of respectful maternity care ?”maximum score i.e. 39.5% response in the item [tab-1].

Table-1-Item wise distribution of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding respectful maternity care

SL NO	ITEMS, AREA – 1	CORRECT RESPONSE	WRONG RESPONSE	ITEM DIFFICULTY
	CONCEPT OF RESPECTFUL MATERNITY CARE			
1.	What do you mean by respectful maternity care ?	87	49	0.63
2.	When a mother’s Self respect is preserved by ?	103	33	0.75
3.	Which one is the wrong statement about respectful maternity care services?	84	52	0.61
4.	Which one aspect is not included in respectful Maternity care ?	76	60	0.55
1.	Which one is not a component of respectful maternity care ?	54	82	0.39

Item wise analysis of knowledge of postnatal mothers correct responses regarding rights of childbearing women to information, informed consent, privacy showed that , maximum 57 % of postnatal mothers were response correctly towards the item “Which situation indicating that mother’s privacy is secured ? ”, 50 % was the correct responded in the item “What is the means of providing equality in care? ” . While 52% was obtained right responds on items “Which one should not to be practiced by health personnel during care?”. & similar to 52% responded towards “Which one is not required for effective communication?”& the same score in the item “Which of the following is not an example of “Good access to skilled attendance” ? .the item “What is the means of providing equality in care? ” . situation indicating that mother’s privacy is secured ? ”, 50 % was the correct responded in care” ? While 52% was the obtained right responds on items “Which one should not to be practiced by health personnel during care?”. & similar to 52% responded towards “Which one is not required for effective communication?”& the same score in the item “Which of the following is not an example of “Good access to skilled attendance” ? . An equal 50%response in the items “Which statement is not a rights of childbearing women ?”& “Who will give consent for Care? ” respectively.53% responded to the item “When an informed consent is valid ?” , 47.% postnatal mothers responded “Which one procedure is not required an informed consent? ”, 48.52% of correct responses to the item . 47%“Which one is not the correct form providing an information to a client ?”. Maximum correct responded 54.% of postnatal mothers to the item “To whom the health personnel should need to provide care first ?” & “Which one is not the real reason of fear among women for hospital delivery ?” respectively.[tab-2]

Tab-2- Item wise distribution of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding respectful maternity care

Sl. No	ITEMS, AREAS-2	CORRECT RESPONSE	WRONG RESPONSE	ITEM DIFFICULTY
	RIGHT OF CHILDBEARING WOMEN TO HAVE INFORMATION, INFORMED CONSENT, PRIVACY			
2.	What is the means of providing equality in care?	69	67	0.5
3.	Which one should not to be practiced by health personnel during care?	67	69	0.42
4.	Which one is not required for effective Communication ?	72	64	0.52
5.	Which of the following is not an example of ‘Good access to skilled attendance’?	72	64	0.52
6.	Which statement is not a rights of childbearing women ?	68	68	0.5
7.	Who will give consent for Care?	68	68	0.5
8.	When an informed consent is valid ?	73	63	0.53
9.	Which one procedure is not required an informed consent?	64	72	0.47
10.	Which one is not the correct form providing an information to a client ?	66	70	0.45
11.	To whom the health personnel should need to provide care first ?	64	72	0.47
12.	Which one is not the real reason of fear among women for hospital delivery?	74	62	0.54
13.	Which situation indicating that mother’s privacy is secured?	78	58	0.57
14.	Which one is not the real reason of fear among women for hospital delivery ?	73	63	0.53

percentage wise distribution of childbearing women to right for timely care to the highest attainable level of health “Which one situations is not an example of violation of dignity ? ” 67 % mean by respectful maternity care 63% , Which of the following is not an example of non- dignified care ?in the item “Which one measures might provide comfort to a mother during labour ?” & “When the baby is in a good condition, a mother could assume which one position during labour ? ” 65%respectively and.” A mother in labour unable to cooperate, need which type of behaviour from health personnel ? ‘61 % Which one is the wrong procedure should avoided during caring a pregnant women?, had 61 % . Likewise in the item ‘Which is the statement indicating a timely health care services? ‘58 % & Which one is not an example of neglect in care ? had 47% & ‘ An pregnant mother with AIDS needs which type of confidential care ?’58 % . During transferring a mother from one unit to other, for

which activity health personnel should not remain responsible. In all other areas of ‘‘ right for timely care to the highest attainable level of health there had an moderate level of percentage of result found need awareness about RMC .[tab-3]

Tab-3-Item wise distribution of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding respectful maternity care

SL. NO	ITEMS, AREAS-3	CORRECT RESPONSE	WRONG RESPONSE	ITEM DIFFICULTY
	RIGHT FOR TIMELY CARE TO THE HIGHEST ATTAINABLE LEVEL OF HEALTH			
15.	Which one situations is not an example of violation of dignity ?	72	64	0.52
16.	How do you make a mother to feel comfort at the time of labor?	71	65	0.52
17.	In which position mother feel comfort during early stage of labor ?	77	59	0.56
18.	If a mother is unable to cooperate in labor, the, follow health care personnel should need which right option?	64	72	0.47
19.	Which is an example of wrong action during hospital procedure for a pregnant mother ?	77	59	0.56
20.	Which is the statement indicating a timely health care services?	79	57	0.58
21.	Which one is not an example of neglect in care ?	83	53	0.61
22.	A AIDS affected pregnant women in labor need which type of care ?	79	57	0.58
23.	A AIDS affected pregnant women in labor need which type of care ?	75	61	0.55
24.	During transferring a mother from one unit to other, for which activity health personnel should not remain responsible?	67	69	0.49

Item wise distribution of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding prevention of disrespect and abuse showed that maximum correct response 61% in ‘‘Which group are involving in awareness campaign regarding respectful maternity Care? &‘‘For involvement of self-care in community, which health advice should not provided ?’’ highest score 67% of postnatal mother responded correctly in the item’’ to the item ‘‘How can you prevent disrespect and abuse to you?’’

60% of postnatal mother responded to item ‘‘At community level to prevent abuse what steps should follow ‘‘.

It indicates that postnatal mothers had a moderate level of knowledge regarding prevention of disrespect & abuse. Need more awareness about the respectful maternity services.

Tab-4-Item wise distribution of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding respectful maternity care

SL. NO	ITEMS , AREA-4	CORRECT RESPONSE	WRONG RESPONSE	ITEM DIFFICULTY
	PREVENTION OF DISRESPECT AND ABUSE			
25.	Which group are involving in awareness campaign regarding respectful maternity Care?	83	53	0.61
26.	For involvement of self-care in community, which health advice should not provided ?	89	47	0.65
27.	At community level to prevent abuse what steps should follow ?	82	54	0.6
28.	How can you prevent disrespect and abuse to you?	92	44	0.67

There was no significant association of level of knowledge with their demographic characteristics of postnatal mother regarding respectful maternity care(RMC).

DISCUSSION

The first objective study was to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding respectful maternity care. The mean knowledge level was (17.71 ± 2.42) among postnatal mothers shows that they had poor knowledge about Respectful Maternity Care.

This study findings was similar to the findings of the author Blessy Mathew (14)conducted a study on “A Study to Assess the Knowledge on Respectful Maternal Care Among the Health Workers Working in Selected Hospital/Health Centers at Meerut” showed that 15(50%) health workers Having Moderate Knowledge and there was only significant association with number of deliveries whereas there is no significant association between age, sex, education, years of experience, area of working and attending any midwifery related training.

Conclusion

RMC is essential for pregnant women to optimize the quality of health care. Sometimes, healthcare providers may normalize disrespectful treatment during childbirth, which intrudes on basic human rights. As childbirth is a critical event in the life of a mother, traumatic childbirth experiences may negatively affect the mental and physical health of women. In this study, the participants had poor level of Knowledge regarding RMC during labor and childbirth. Most of them were not informed about their healthcare providers or were exposed to unnecessary interventions that negatively affected the mother and her child. Thus, participatory actions must be ensured by policymakers, leaders, and healthcare providers to promote RMC at public hospitals in Odisha. More and more awareness programmes can be organized to create awareness among mothers. .

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